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Influence of Work-Related Stress on Marital Adjustment of Working Class-Women in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of working class-women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The study used a descriptive survey research approach. The study was led by two hypotheses and two research questions. 112 women who worked for the Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Councils made up the study's population. Using the census sample approach, all 112 of the women employed by the Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Councils were chosen for the study. Data was gathered using a self-created tool called the "Work-Related Stress and Marital Adjustment Questionnaire." Two specialists in counselling psychology and measurement and evaluation from Rivers State University in Port Harcourt assessed the instrument's face and content validity. Using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation technique, the instrument's test-retest reliability was determined to be 0.78. Mean was used to analyze the research questions, while Z-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Results showed that: work-related stress influenced marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent. Also, work-related stress influenced marital adjustment of working-class women who were young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent. Recommendations were made that: Organizations should make provisions to cushion the effect of work-related stress on both the low and high income earning women for better adjustment in their marital life, and that both the working-class women who were young and old in marriage should not be exposed to much work-related stress to avoid its negative impact on their marital adjustment.

Keywords: Adjustment, Marital adjustment, Stress, Women, Work-related stress

INTRODUCTION

Job stress is not a new issue when it comes to occupation or employment of people in the society. In fact, job stress is a well-researched global phenomenon and an emerging problem also in developing countries like Nigeria, and teaching has been identified as a profession that is laden with stress (Mathew, 2017). Job or occupational Stress, if not well managed can lead to poor physical, emotional and mental health (KetsdeVries, 2019). Severe job stress can lower productivity and in severe cases lead to death. It has impact on marital relationships. According to Kemey, Story and Bradbury (2015) emotional support from close friends and families offers a buffer that enables individuals to cope with negative outcomes that stress offers especially on marital relationship.

Work, marriage, and marital satisfaction are without a doubt multifaceted. This is in view of the fact that work and marriage are two key areas through which most adults draw their pleasures in life. Such legal emotional commitment and these complications therefore determine the level of adjustment among adults (Folkman, 2013). This is so important because all marriages are directed towards happiness in one way or the other. Every marriage has expectations, some are reasonable, some are unreasonable, which could be because of the many facets of marriage (Neff and Kamey, 2015). However, the study revealed that marriage offered a greater protection to man than the woman (Jamabo & Ordu, 2012).

One of the most important and significant influences on the longevity and stability of married life is thought to be marital adjustment. In his 2013 publication, Folkman was able to demonstrate that higher ratings on marital status pleasantness are linked, and consequently, low levels of personal adjustment and high levels of marital adjustment are especially linked to increased levels of depression and other forms of psychopathology. Marital adjustment is the current level of positively toned affection between spouses and their satisfaction with the marital relationship (Mason, 2015). Marital adjustment may therefore be defined as the extent to which the couple become well-settled, happy and indeed successfully completes several tasks in marriage.

Work and family are two major concerns in our lives, and a favourable work-family interface could enhance the psycho-social quality of couples. Perhaps, it is understandable that due to the multiple tasks working and performing domestic duties entail, women end up having a lot of problems such as depression, marital stress among others. It is for these reasons that these problems could impinge on spouse ability to give required attention to homes and marital life, as well as decreasing their productivity at workplaces. According to Mason (2015) employment of working class women impacts personality of women and their relationship with family and they are also vulnerable to confront crisis of marital adjustment.

Another scholarly research work revealed that women responded more often to challenges with regard to work interference with family, and vice versa, and work and family pressure (James, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

As a result of the worldwide economic recession, which has led to greater rivalry and the closure of several public and private firms, Nigerians today are afflicted with worry, wrath, irritation, general impatience, and aggressive behaviour everywhere. Recently, we have seen so many marriages chattering due to lack of attention from spouses, work stress, lack of closeness, lack of communication, lack of concern in spousal experiences from both husbands and wives in Port Harcourt Metropolis and the world at large. Women are supposed to stay at home and take care of the house in Nigerian traditional society. Nonetheless, women have undergone revolutionary transformations as a result of education. Women are increasingly choosing to work in some capacity in order to support their families financially. There appear to be problems coming from the obligations and expectations of marriage and job when women leave their husbands' company, in contrast to the way things were done in the past, to work outside the home. Since married working-class women must fulfil several responsibilities as employees, which leaves them with little time for other responsibilities in their personal lives, such as taking care of the home, These disagreements might not be unrelated to the stress individuals experience at work. Many women nowadays are become more self-reliant and are no longer depending much on their partners for all their needs financially. These women are usually assigned duties in their offices in addition to their domestic functions which tend to add to their stress level at work, and thus demand some level of adjustment in their marital life where necessary. It is on this note that this study sought to determine the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of working class-women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of working class-women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which work-related stress influences marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

2. Examine the extent to which work-related stress influences marital adjustment of working-class women who are young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does work-related stress influence marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. To what extent does work-related stress influences marital adjustment of working-class women who are young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference in the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of working-class women who are young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Stress

Stress is a condition of mental or emotional tension brought on by difficult or unfavourable situations. It is a great worry that may be caused by an excessive work demand which could result in burnout. Stress is defined as a state of discomfort, tension, or emotional pain that occurs when a person encounters a situation that presents a demand that the person must meet but for which his or her abilities and resources seem insufficient. This is one of the more widely accepted definitions of stress. People often experience stress in their daily lives. According to James (2017), stress is anything that might throw off a person's own equilibrium or an action or circumstance that puts unique psychological demands on them. He went on to say that stress might be thought of as a troublesome circumstance for which there is absolutely no remedy. This suggests that when a person's coping mechanisms are insufficient to satisfy particular problems in life.

Aspects of Influence Relating to Work-Related Stress

Some of the major causes and sources of work-related stress among couples, according to Amalu and Bekomson (2020) are highlighted as follows:

1. **Poor interpersonal relationship:** They will inevitably be under stress due to the different complicated connections between the spouses and other people, including his coworkers. When team members don't get along, for instance, it can lead to difficult situations, tension, and bad decision-making (Wooll, 2022).
2. **Poor work conditions:** Poor lighting and ventilation, dirty restrooms, excessive noise and dust, hazardous gases and fumes, insufficient safety precautions, and other issues might be encountered by the worker. Stress results from the physiological and psychological imbalances caused by all of these undesirable circumstances. Employees endure innumerable denials over office furnishings. Some people utilise rooms with deteriorating roofs as offices. In support of this notion, Wooll (2022) said that working from home and being distracted by things around the house might lead to a lot of stress, or a loud office makes it difficult to concentrate.
3. **Salaries and allowances:** In several states, salaries have not been paid. Allowances and primary pay are sometimes reduced. Couples may do other things when they are unable to support their family. Some spouses go months without getting paid. KetsdeVries (2019) asserts that financial difficulties might lead to stress.
4. **Personality type:** Excessive competitive urge to do more tasks in less time is a hallmark of a Type "A" personality. An individual with a type "A" personality has a persistent feeling of urgency and internalised animosity, which can drive them insane with their schedules and goals. He is susceptible to stress and heart disease because of his ingrained insecurity, intense impatience, social domination, excess of regression, and most importantly, the suppression of psychological energy. Even after

formal hours, such a teacher continues to work. He sometimes takes on many tasks at once. He truly exhausts himself due to his workload (Amalu & Bekomson, 2020).

5. **Family problems:** These may exacerbate stress. A staff that has lived an unstable life going from one devastating psychological problem to another may be stressed because of this bombardment. Those who would like to kill themselves in order to stop suffering in this world are examples of having core issues. In some families, there may be problem between the couples and their children (Amalu & Bekomson, 2020).
6. **Denied or delayed promotion:** Promotion has been recognized as one of the best rewarding factors in the workplace. This increases the morale of the workers and also they also feel that the management of their organizations appreciate their service. It also makes them feel they are appreciated in the place and will therefore, be in a position to work hard. This has an undesirable side effect of fostering the 'we feeling' and the workers start considering it as our organization and not their organization (Omeje, 2017).
7. **Role conflict:** This happens when a job holder must concurrently adhere to several expectations that are incompatible, unconnected, contradictory, or inconsistent with one another to the point that fulfilling one set of responsibilities makes fulfilling another set or dimension challenging. When a teacher serves as a parent, counsellor, administrator, or pastor, role conflict may occur. A detailed job description is necessary to prevent role conflict and increase productivity and efficiency.

Marital Adjustment

Succumbing is certainly an important facet of wedded bliss, but it isn't always all that painless. The very core of adjustment is completely distinct from what is said about it or what is said in its name. It became complicated when the couples themselves do not know the real meaning or concept of marriage because of the open ended roles and no prescription rules as sometimes both are working. Sometimes the wife develop cases of identity crisis since she is turned to being a mere house wife due to inability to cooperate which lead to dissatisfaction and conflicts. Four major dimensions of marital satisfaction are marital partner, sexual, financial and in-law relationship satisfaction (Omeje, 2017). Marital adjustment was postulated to be associated with several marital variables concerning dyadic adjustment (Abbasi, 2017).

Theoretical Review

Social Exchange theory

Davlembayeva and Alamanos (2023) stated that Social Exchange theory is a theory that expresses the social conduct in dyadic and collective interactions based on principles of self cost-benefit analysis of relations. However, the greatest importance of this work might be considered in the context of its potential to contribute to the development of the future research in the field of marital and family relationships, and to enhance the theoretical definition of the subject area.

Based on a net analysis of over a hundred studies of married couples, it was identified that spouses and couples attain specific results which are part and partial of one of the three major domains of marital influence: It includes the personality traits as well as experiences of spouses prior to marriage; the stress factors and situations that couples face after marriage; and the emotions as well as the communication style which the spouses use while adjusting themselves and the stress they face. The social exchange theory is relevant to this study because it conceives a mental relationship as an exchange system in terms of reciprocal behaviour involving trust, unequal power, norms, among others in relation to the social conditions for interpersonal behaviour.

Concept of Work Related Stress

Work-related stress, according to James (2017) is directly proportional to the degree of compatibility between an individual's coping capabilities and the demands of the work environment in which they are required to operate. Similarly, Woll (2022) emphasized that work-related stress occurs when one's mind and body respond high to work demands he/she is unable to cope with. This may include too many tasks, target workloads and tight deadline, which involves more pressure thereby increase work-place stress. Additionally, stress leads to burnout at work, which manifests as symptoms like trouble focussing and

concentrating, physical and mental tiredness, headaches and migraines, elevated heart rate and blood pressure, low morale, and a negative attitude, among others (Wooll, 2022)

Concept of Working-Class

Working class women refer to socio-economic term, describing persons in order of the jobs they do that pay poorly and need little physical effort or expertise (James, 2021). Working-class Clerical, retail, and low-skilled manual labour occupations are among the services-related jobs that are stated to have lower educational requirements (James, 2021). In view of the foregoing, there are various types of working class, blue collar, white collar among others. The term blue collar describes a group of workers. Blue-collar workers are seen as members of the working class (Dhir, 2023). Furthermore, blue collar jobs command high salaries because they are highly skilled and educated.

Concept of High and Low Working Class

The high working class maybe considered as a wealthy and powerful upper class that own and controls the means of production. The lower classes are those workers who rely on low paying jobs. Agard (2023) maintained that high class means enough income, accumulated wealth, in which the individual will never have to worry about basic survival needs. The reverse will be the care of the lower class that may have low paid jobs and struggling for survival needs.

Concept of Young and Old Working Class

The young working-class are those people that are new in the job, with limited experience, but may have learned the power of social media. Old workers are those who have had years of experience and have benefitted from education and on-the-job training, although they might not be as tech-savvy as younger individuals (Schawbel, 2018). But according to Vickerstaff and Loretto (2017), the case for extending the working age has mostly characterised older people as troublesome, and their present retirement patterns as self-centred, ignorant, and out of date, posing a danger to social services.

Empirical Review

Work-Related Stress and Marital Adjustment of Low and High Income Earning Working-Class Women

White and Rogers (2010) found that low income status reduced both male and female perceived family support and adversely affected their marital happiness and thus called on social work intervention programmes concerning low income families to address the economic problems of such families and help in management of their resources and relationship issues. There is a correlation between economic stress and marital conflict and marital maladjustment (Hughes, 2014). Families with high income are in a better position to offload tasks related to the home, and also pay for marriage counseling services in case of a confrontation (Trail & Kamey, 2012). Also, a high income gives the couple the opportunity to devote some time to their mutual interests and turn ideas about their relationship into practice. Whereas the daily hassles of low-income couples are all the chronic daily hassles that come with having little money and they cannot avoid prioritizing the survival aspect of their relationship over the relationship improvement aspect (KetsdeVries, 2019).

Work-Related Stress and Marital Adjustment of Young and Old Working-Class Women

Duration of marriage also known as marital lifespan has been pointed out literature as a predictor of marital satisfaction. According to Peleg (2018), marriage longevity is very important since family duration is established as one of the most influential factors concerning family satisfaction. The result of one of the researches reveal that marital satisfaction increases with the duration of marriage (James, 2017).

Umberson (2015) defined marital quality as a development trajectory that fluctuates over the course of the marital union. He also stated that marital quality deteriorates with time and that age plays a great role than does marital duration. Cross sectional studies reveal that marital satisfaction is high at the beginning of the pre-children stage, declines at the mid parental stage and rises at the post children stage of marriage (Omeje, 2017). Jalovaara (2012) thought that by some theoretical considerations we can predict that divorces should decrease with age as the length of the marriage increases.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey research approach. According to Dike (2017), a descriptive survey research design is an effort to collect and analyse information on a group, an area, an event, or a social institution. Because it allowed the researcher to characterise the impact of work-related stress on working-class women's marital adjustment without changing any of the variables, this research design is ideal for the study. The population of the study comprised 112 women working in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The population was made up of 67 women working in Obio/Akpor Local Government Council and 45 women working in Port Harcourt Local Government Council (Source: Administration Offices in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Council Headquarters, 2023). The sample size of the study was all the 112 women working in Port Harcourt Metropolis (67 in Obio/Akpor and 45 in Port Harcourt City Council) which was selected using the Census sampling technique.

A self-developed instrument titled: Work-Related Stress and Marital Adjustment Questionnaire (QRSMAQ) was used for data collection. There were two parts to the instrument. While part B focused on working-class women's marital adjustment and work-related stress, section A was devoted to demographic data. Section B contained sixteen items prepared in a modified four-point likert type scale ranging from Very High Extent (VHE) = 4 points, Moderate Extent (ME) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point. The face and content validity of the instrument was determined by two experts in Counselling Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Test-retest reliability using Person Product Moment Correlation yielded coefficient of 0.78 for the instrument. This figure was deemed sufficient to conduct the investigation. Trained research assistants assisted in administering and retrieving the instrument from the respondents. The Z-test at the 0.05 level of significance was used to evaluate the null hypotheses, and the mean and standard deviation were used to assess the research questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *To what extent does work-related stress influence marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 1: Mean Ratings on Influence of Work-related Stress on Marital Adjustment of Low and High Income Earning Working-class Women

S/No.	Items	Low Income Women (n = 75)			High Income Women (n = 37)		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Work pressure affects my ability to attend to my husband at home.	2.75	0.72	High Extent	2.71	0.69	High Extent
2.	Workload makes me to go home late almost every day which my husband doesn't like.	2.67	0.65	High Extent	2.70	0.70	High Extent
3.	Waking up very early in the morning on daily basis tend to affect my marital life.	2.44	0.62	Low Extent	2.40	0.60	Low Extent
4.	Duty calls in my work place tend to affect my relationship with my husband.	2.74	0.70	High Extent	2.70	0.67	High Extent
5.	Work overload makes me feel unhappy even at home most times.	2.70	0.68	High Extent	2.67	0.66	High Extent
6.	Promotion denial affects my emotion even at home.	2.76	0.72	High Extent	2.73	0.70	High Extent
Grand \bar{X}		2.68		High Extent	2.65		High Extent

Source: Field Data, 2023.

Criterion Mean = 2.50

From the data in Table 1, it can be observed that out of the six items (items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6) on influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis, only the mean score for item 3 (\bar{X} = 2.44 for low income and 2.40 for high income earning working-class women) was below the criterion mean (2.50), while the mean scores for other items (items 1, 2, 4, 5 and 6) are higher than the criterion mean of 2.50. With the grand mean of 2.68 and 2.65 for the low and high income earning working-class women higher than the criterion mean (2.50), it was concluded that work-related stress influences marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does work-related stress influences marital adjustment of working-class women who are young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 2: Mean Ratings on Influence of Work-related Stress on Marital Adjustment of Working-class Women who are Young and Old in Marriage

S/No.	Items	Young Women in Marriage (n = 42)			Old Women in Marriage (n = 70)		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Work pressure affects my ability to attend to my husband at home.	2.60	0.81	High Extent	2.53	0.74	High Extent
2.	Workload makes me to go home late almost every day which my husband doesn't like.	2.59	0.76	High Extent	2.67	0.81	High Extent
3.	Waking up very early in the morning on daily basis tend to affect my marital life.	2.54	0.72	High Extent	2.57	0.66	High Extent
4.	Duty calls in my work place tend to affect my relationship with my husband.	2.60	0.74	High Extent	2.67	0.79	High Extent
5.	Work overload makes me feel unhappy even at home most times.	2.62	0.82	High Extent	2.65	0.87	High Extent
6.	Promotion denial affects my emotion even at home.	2.65	0.84	High Extent	2.60	0.89	High Extent
Grand \bar{X}		2.60		High Extent	2.62		High Extent

Source: Field Data, 2023.

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 2 revealed that the mean scores for the working-class women who are young and old in marriage on all the items (items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6) are higher than the criterion mean (2.50) and are remarked as high extent. It was therefore concluded that work-related stress influences marital adjustment of working-class women who are young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 3: Z-Test Analysis of Difference in the Influence of Work-Related Stress on Marital Adjustment of Low and High Income Earning Working-class Women

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	z-value	p-value	α	Remark
Low Income Earning Working-class Women	75	2.68	0.68	110	0.222	0.824	0.05	Not Sig.
High Income Earning Working-class Women	37	2.65	0.67					

From Table 3, it can be observed that at 0.05 level of significance and 110 degree of freedom, the z-value = 0.222 and p-value = 0.824. Since the p-value of 0.824 > 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was therefore accepted which implies that there is no significant difference in the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of working-class women who are young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Table 4: Z-Test Analysis of Difference in the Influence of Work-Related Stress on Marital Adjustment of Low and High Income Earning Working-class Women

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	z-value	p-value	α	Remark
Young Women in Marriage	42	2.60	0.78	110	-0.131	0.896	0.05	Not Sig.
Old Women in Marriage	70	2.62	0.79					

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Results shown in Table 1 for research question 1 revealed that work-related stress influences marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent. Furthermore, it was observed from the test of hypothesis 1 as presented in Table 3 that there was no significant difference in the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This result could be because work-related stress affects all workers irrespective of level of income. This result seem to be in disagreement with Folkman and Lazarus (2016) who revealed that high-income couples may easily afford marriage counselling services if they have marital issues, and they have greater financial means to lessen the load of home tasks.

According to a Chinese study, relationships were negatively impacted by decreased family income (Omeje, 2017). The level of living in China's cities has been rising dramatically in recent years. According to a psychological viewpoint, income-related stress had a detrimental effect on spouses' relationships and raised interpersonal conflict, which decreased marital satisfaction (Kemey, Story & Bradbury, 2015). Folkman (2013), however, discovered a clear positive correlation between family

income and marriage quality; that is, urban Chinese couples with lower incomes reported less marital satisfaction than those with greater incomes.

Result for research question 2 as shown in Table 2 revealed that work-related stress influenced marital adjustment of working-class women who are young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent. It was further found from the results for test of hypothesis 2 as presented in Table 4 that there was no significant difference in the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of working-class women who were young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This result could be because number of years in marriage or marital longevity may not determine the nature of job to be assigned to an employee in his/her organization. In support of the result of this study, Mathew (2015) explained that the employment in addition to their personalities, working-class women also had an impact on their family relationships and were more likely to experience marital adjustment issues. According to one study, women frequently face more challenges in relation to work-family conflict, family, and work-related expectations and pressures (James, 2017). This can be as a result of the persistent evidence that stress at work affects mood at home (Dunenci in Ben-Ari & Lavee, 2013).

CONCLUSION

This study which examined the influence of work-related stress on marital adjustment of working class-women in Port Harcourt Metropolis revealed that work-related stress influences marital adjustment of low and high income earning working-class women, and working-class women who are young and old in marriage in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent. It was therefore concluded that work-related stress is an influential factor of marital adjustment of working-class women in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Implication for Counselling

In considerations of the findings of the study and conclusion drawn, the following are the implications for counselling:

1. Organizations could be determined by the findings of this study to engage the services of a professional counsellor who will engage the workers on a regular career talk, especially as it concerns work-related stress and its management approaches for the well-being of the workers.
2. The findings of the study could also prompt individual workers to seek for profession counselling on issues of marital adjustment in relation to the nature of their jobs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Organizations should make provisions to cushion the effect of work-related stress on both the low and high income earning women for better adjustment in their marital life.
2. Both the working-class women who are young and old in marriage should not be exposed to much work-related stress to avoid its negative impact on their marital adjustment.

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